

FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON

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ANNOTATION

The Python programming language has changed so much in recent years that it has covered many areas. For example, Python is considered one of the most reliable programming languages in the fields of Data Science, Deep learning, Machine learning, Computer vision and AI. When working with data in artificial intelligence, neural networks, and in the above areas, visualization of problem solutions helps to visualize the accuracy of the solution. The Matplotlib library helps us to create a visual image. In this dissertation, we will focus on how to process an image, how massive it is, and how to change the contrast in image processing.

Keywords: python, matplotlib, opencvpython, jupyter, numpy, pandas, pytorch, array, pseudocolor schemas.

Introduction

Python can detect and recognize your face from a photo or video

Face recognition applications include face unlocking(face id), security and Defense, etc. Doctors and healthcare professionals use facial recognition to access patients ' medical records and history and to better diagnose diseases.

Main part

In this python project, we want to create a machine learning model that recognizes people in images. We use face_recognition API and OpenCV in our project.

Libraries

- Python – 3.x
- cv2 – 4.5.2
- numpy – 1.20.3
- face_recognition – 1.3.0

We use the following command to install the above packages.

1. pip install numpy opencv-python
2. pip install dlib
3. pip install face_recognition

Project data collection

We can implement this face recognition project using our own dataset. For this project, I used my friends image as a dataset.

Steps to develop a face recognition model

Before proceeding, let's understand what is face detection and detection.

Face recognition is the process of identifying or verifying a person's face from photographs and video footage.

Face detection is defined as the process of identifying and extracting faces (location and size) from an image to use a face detection algorithm.

The face recognition method is used to identify unique displayed features in an image. In most cases, the face image has already been removed, cut, scaled and turned gray. Face recognition includes 3 stages: face recognition, feature release, Face Recognition.

OpenCV is an open source library written in C++. It includes the implementation of various algorithms and deep neural networks used for computer vision tasks.

1. We prepare a data set

We will create 2 directories, we will try training. We need to make sure that the images we choose represent the facial features well enough for the classifier.

Let's test the model, take a picture called friends and place it in our "common_picture" directory.

2. Training ie we will teach the model

- First we import the necessary modules.
- The `face_recognition` library contains various utilities that help with the face recognition process.
- Now we create 2 lists that store the names of the images (persons) and their face encodings.

```
path = "./training_pict/"
```

```
known_names = []
```

```
known_name_encodings = []
```

```
images = os.listdir(path)
```

- A face encoding is a vector of values representing important dimensions between distinguishing features of a face, such as the distance between the eyes, the width of the forehead, and so on.

- We loop through each image in our `training_image` directory, extract the name of the person in the image, compute its face encoding vector, and store the data in the corresponding lists.

```
for _ in images:
```

```
    image = fr.load_image_file(path + _)
```

```
    image_path = path + _
```

```
    encoding = fr.face_encodings(image)[0]
```

```
    known_name_encodings.append(encoding)
```

```
    known_names.append(os.path.splitext(os.path.basename(image_path))[0].c
apitalize())
```

3. Test the model on a test data set

- As mentioned above, our dataset in our `public_image` directory contains only 1 image with all the persons in it.

- Cv2 reads the test image using the imread() method.

```
test_image = "./umumiy_rasm/do'stlar.jpg"
```

```
image = cv2.imread(test_image)
```

▪ The face_recognition library provides a useful method called face_locations() that locates the coordinates (left, bottom, right, top) of each face detected in the image. Using these location values, we can easily find face encodings

```
face_locations = fr.face_locations(image)
```

```
face_encodings = fr.face_encodings(image, face_locations)
```

▪ We consider each face location and its encoding in the image. We then compare this encoding with the encodings of the faces in the "training_image" dataset.

▪ Then calculate the face distance, that is, we determine the similarity between the encoding of the test image and the images of the training_image. Now we select the minimum value distance from it, which indicates that the face in the image common_image is one of the faces in the training_image dataset.

▪ Now, using the methods in the cv2 module, draws a rectangle with the coordinates of the face position

```
for (top, right, bottom, left), face_encoding in zip(face_locations,  
face_encodings):
```

```
    matches = fr.compare_faces(known_name_encodings, face_encoding)
```

```
    name = ""
```

```
    face_distances = fr.face_distance(known_name_encodings, face_encoding)
```

```
    best_match = np.argmin(face_distances)
```

```
    if matches[best_match]:
```

```
        name = known_names[best_match]
```

```
        cv2.rectangle(image, (left, top), (right, bottom), (0, 0, 255), 2)
```

```
        cv2.rectangle(image, (left, bottom - 15), (right, bottom), (0, 0, 255),
```

```
cv2.FILLED)
```

```
font = cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_DUPLEX
```

```
cv2.putText(image, name, (left + 6, bottom - 6), font, 1.0, (255, 255, 255), 1)
```

Shows the image using the imshow() method of the Cv2 module.

```
cv2.imshow("Natija", image)
```

Tasvirni imwrite() usuli yordamida joriy ishchi katalogimizga saqlaydi.

```
cv2.imwrite("./Natija_rasm.jpg", image)
```

```
cv2.waitKey(0)
```

```
cv2.destroyAllWindows()
```

References

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